

STRUCTURAL-FUNCTIONAL COMPARISON OF PHYTONYMS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: In this article outlines the scientific basis on the functional comparison of phytonyms in translation from English into Uzbek. Also, Phytonyms are seen as lexical units of a special order, and nouns as terms-words and terms-phrases. Such a two-way approach to phytonyms makes it possible to analyze their lexical and lexical-semantic units. On the one hand, when translating phytonyms, lexical changes and lexical-semantic changes are used, on the other.

Keywords: linguistics, phytonyms, translation, translation transformations, equivalent, scientific analysis.

It is known that the national picture of the world, which is often used in linguistic research, is formed by geographical, climatic, natural living conditions, professions, traditions, customs, rituals, rituals and other important components of human life, without which no concept exists and cannot exist and be complete. The main area of linguistic research, which includes the comparative study of languages for translation in terms of determining the degree of isomorphism and allomorphy, achieving understanding in terms of equivalence, conformity and intercultural communication, is the national picture of the world. "*Man knew things and phenomena in the process of mastering the objective world. For him, since plants were a source of food, served as a shelter, were used for medicinal purposes, he was especially closely associated with them.*" Human observations and experiments have found expression in the language: plants got their name in accordance with the selected motivational characteristics.

One of the pressing problems in the history of phytonymy is vocabulary research - this is the definition of the semantic extension "*phytonym*", since there is nothing generally accepted interpretation of this term, despite its widespread use in linguistics. Phytonyms are defined as botanical units of nomenclature and against scientific naming units of plants. Words belonging to this lexical group have important characteristics that must be taken into account when learning. The reason linguists pay special attention to the plant world is that plants occupy one of the main places in human life by culture. The use of phytonyms continues mythological, religious and literary traditions. Phytomorphism is associated with the initial form of thinking, from which the concepts derived

from this form are transferred in the language. Phytonyms continue to attract the attention of many researchers, and their study is now widespread. They are considered in different types of speech (literary, poetic, scientific and political; the material is based only on one language and in comparison between languages. Despite the variety of approaches used by different types, according to the authors, they are flora Universal, which makes it possible to consider one of the most ancient methods of modeling.

Along with other components, the life of people has always been inextricably linked with the plant world. According to A.Hathe¹ "... when comparing languages, one can single out universal and specific linguistic means of describing reality, which makes it possible to reveal the peculiarities of the national picture of the world of each people. In this work, we were more interested in the problems of translating plant names, i.e. phytonyms, from the point of view of translation. By phytonym we mean special names that are denoted by plant names. They can include a wide variety of plant species. According to N.Z. Pazlitdinova² "these are the names of trees, the names of herbs and herbaceous plants, the names of melons, flowers and shrubs. The named author gives 8 different groups of plants, depending on their belonging to the botanical family." The purpose of this article is to identify the most common language tools and terms used in the description of plants and methods for translating from English into Uzbek. The following research methods have been used to study various aspects of the translation of phytonyms:

- ❖ *method of dictionary definitions selected material;*
- ❖ *comparative typological method for determining the types of inter-linguistic correspondence at the lexical and lexical-semantic levels;*
- ❖ *lexical analysis method for studying the semantics of phytonyms;*
- ❖ *methodology for determining the types of linguistic semantic correspondence based on the structural theory of the specificity / difference of the seminal Organization of the lexical meaning of lexical (including borrowed) units of different languages.*

It should be noted that it is advisable to distinguish the names of phytonutrients and the names of their varieties. The names of their varieties are closer to anthroponyms, especially in Uzbek. When translating such units, preference

¹ Hathe a.a. Nominations of the plant world in cognitive and linguoculturological aspects: on the material of the Russian and Adyghe languages: author. Cand. Philol. Sciences. - Maikop, 2010. - 26 p..

² Pazlitdinova N.Z. About phytonyms of the Uzbek language, denoting gourds // <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/o-fitonimam-uzbekskogo-yazykabonachayuschih-nazvaniya-bahchevyh/viewer>

should be given to the names of the varieties of phytonyms. Thus, phytonyms are considered as lexical units of a special order, and nouns as terms-words and terms-phrases in our article, phytonyms are considered as lexical units of a special order, that is, Terms – words and terms-phrases. Such a two-way approach to the study of phytonyms makes it possible to analyze their lexical and lexical-semantic units. On the one hand, lexical changes are used in the translation of phytonyms, and on the other, lexical-semantic changes. Since the main part of the phytonyms comes from Latin, it requires the use of other translation transformations. Translation problems associated with the transfer of plant names are reduced to the following: when transferring plant names consisting of one word, there is the following correspondence:

1. The name of one-word plants. In this case, in translation from English into Uzbek, one name corresponds to one word in translation: Rose, cabbage;
2. In translation, the name of plants, consisting of one word, corresponds to a two-word phrase: creeper, climber;
3. The name of plants, consisting of one word, in translation corresponds to a phrase consisting of three words: perennial; annual; two-year-two-year annuity, etc. The name of the plants consists of one word, which in translation corresponds to a phrase consisting of four components: trailer - erdaermalab ousadigane ousimlik;

The name of the plants, consisting of two words, corresponds to the phrase in translation, and there is an absolute synonym for it, which has a scientific name: water plant and aquatic plant – sudae ousadigane ousimlik, as well as you can use the translation option –water ousimlik, etc.

Thus, the translation of phytonyms, that is, plant names, requires the use of various translation variations. Therefore, the name of plants in the English language can be translated on the basis of a number of changes (transformations), where it is not possible to often observe one name – one word correspondence. There are more differences in English and Uzbek languages than similarities in the names of plants as different systems. The names of plants in English and Uzbek can partially coincide, this phenomenon is clearly manifested in the translation of plant names from the indicated language into Uzbek. At the same time, lexical and lexical-semantic transformations are used in translation. Since the main part of the phytonyms comes from Latin, the use of other types of translation transformations is required. As for borrowing from plant names in English, it should be noted that most of the plant names

come from Latin, while in Uzbek it is common to borrow from Persian and Arabic along with Latin plant names.

References:

1. Nurmanov Fi is an important component of the language picture in the myth-world.// "Topical" Journal Humanities and Natural Sciences Problems " 2015 No. 5-1 p.276-278.
2. Pazlitdinova N.Z. About phytonyms of the Uzbek language, denoting gourds // <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/o-fitonimah-uzbekskogo-yazykaobznachayuschih-nazvaniya-bahchevyh/viewer>
3. Sakhobiddinov s. Systematics of plants. Flowering plants. - Tashkent: teacher, 1966.
4. Sivakova N.A. Lexicographic description of English and Russian phytonyms in an electronic glossary: Author. Cand. Philol. Sciences. - Tyumen, 2004. - 28 p.
5. Hathe a.a. Nominations of the plant world in cognitive and linguoculturological aspects: on the material of the Russian and Adyghe languages: author. Cand. Philol. Sciences. - Maikop, 2010. - 26 p.

